

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

DIAMAS Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors, and Policymakers

Deliverable 6.2

Authors: Sona Lisa Arasteh-Roodsary (OPERAS), Vinciane Gaillard (EUA),
Federica Garbuglia (EUA), Pierre Mounier (OPERAS) Janne Pölönen
(TSV), Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe), Johan Rooryck (cOAlition S),
Bregt Saenen (Science Europe), Graham Stone (Jisc).

Reviewer(s): Remedios Melero and Youngim Jung

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
Jisc	Jisc LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

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Acronyms

ANR	French National Research Agency (French: Agence nationale de la recherche)
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
DFG	German Research Foundation (German: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EUA	European Universities Association
HRČAK	Portal of Croatian Scientific and Professional Journals
IPSP	Institutional Publishers and Publishing Service Provider
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee
OA	Open Access
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for social sciences and humanities
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
POSI	Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure
TSV	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (Finnish: Tieteellisten seurain valtuuskunta)
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization
Universities SHARE	Universities Scholarly Heritage and Access to Research

Executive Summary

This report presents a comprehensive and flexible framework to support Diamond Open Access (OA) in scholarly publishing. Developed as Deliverable 6.2 of the DIAMAS project, funded by the European Union's Horizon WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 research and innovation programme, the report offers recommendations and guidelines tailored to institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers.

The recommendations and guidelines have been co-designed with stakeholders through an extensive collaborative process led by the European University Association (EUA), Science Europe, and OPERAS between December 2023 and November 2024. This co-design approach ensures that the proposed measures address the diverse needs, concerns, and opportunities within the evolving Diamond OA ecosystem.

Collective responsibility and collaboration

Supporting Diamond OA is a shared responsibility among institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers. While each plays a distinct role, their coordinated efforts are essential for the long-term sustainability of this publishing model. The report underscores the importance of collaboration, emphasising that:

- **Institutions** act as 'parent organisations' by providing staff, infrastructure, and academic resources to maintain Diamond OA platforms and repositories.
- **Funders, sponsors, and donors** ensure financial sustainability through policies and investments that enable the continued development of Diamond OA.
- **Policymakers** at regional, national, and EU levels create frameworks that facilitate and incentivise Diamond OA adoption.

Pathways for supporting Diamond OA

To foster a thriving Diamond OA ecosystem, the report outlines strategic pathways for engagement, including:

- Identify reasons and motivations to support Diamond OA and promote its benefits
- Enhance recognition and reward systems
- Invest in the development of monitoring systems and evidence-gathering initiatives
- Sign the Action Plan for Diamond OA
- Support local, national, and community Diamond Capacity Centres
- Engage in the European Diamond Capacity Hub
- Engage in the Global Diamond Open Access Framework

Recommendations and guidelines

The framework aims to guide institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers in their support of Diamond OA. The report organises its recommendations and guidelines in separate, but related categories that reflect the main reasons for research actors to support Diamond OA, including:

- **Positive research cultures:** Institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers share a responsibility to strengthen positive research cultures that reflect core values such as autonomy, freedom, care, collegiality, collaboration, equality, diversity, inclusion, integrity, ethics, openness, and transparency.
- **Economic and financial responsibilities:** Institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers must address economic and financial responsibilities to ensure that scholarly publishing is sustainable and provides societal value.
- **Dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy:** When supporting Diamond OA, institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers must take into account the dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy. This includes both top-down support and bottom-up initiatives.

While comprehensive, the framework remains flexible, allowing different organisations to prioritise actions based on their unique contexts, governance structures, operational models, and available resources. Stakeholders, for instance, may implement recommendations at varied timelines, depending on national policies and institutional readiness.

Conclusion

This report serves as a foundational document for institutions, funders, sponsors, donors, and policymakers committed to supporting Diamond OA. By providing a structured yet adaptable set of recommendations and guidelines, it lays the groundwork for a collaborative effort to reshape scholarly publishing. The continued evolution of Diamond OA will require ongoing dialogue, policy alignment, and resource allocation to ensure its long-term success.

Recommendations and Guidelines at a Glance

Recommendations and guidelines	Institutions	Funders, sponsors, and donors	Policy-makers
Positive research cultures			
Support multilingual and multicultural scholarly communities and their journals, repositories, and platforms	✓	✓	✓
Organise initiatives to promote the benefits of Diamond OA in your institution	✓		
Ensure that your institution's Diamond OA publisher adheres to rigorous quality standards	✓		
Raise awareness about the importance of finding and choosing high-quality Diamond OA publication venues	✓		
Advocate for a more equitable scholarly publishing ecosystem, including Diamond OA through policy change and action			✓
Economic and financial responsibilities			
<i>Sustainable funding</i>			
Make long-term funding commitments	✓	✓	✓
Develop collaborative funding initiatives	✓	✓	✓
Encourage institutions to repurpose savings from institutional, regional or national publishing deals			✓
Consider exploring strategies for a more sustainable budget allocation for the institution's scholarly communication activities	✓		
Seek to innovate funding mechanisms to support improvements in digital transformation			✓

Support open, inclusive and community-owned databases	✓		✓
<i>Cost transparency and control</i>			
Require transparent financial reporting	✓	✓	✓
Invest in cost-effective publishing solutions	✓	✓	✓
Dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy			
<i>Top-down support</i>			
Advocate for public policies	✓	✓	✓
Engage in international collaboration	✓	✓	✓
Create opportunities for knowledge exchange and networking	✓	✓	✓
Strengthen Diamond OA through strategic funding and funding strategies	✓	✓	✓
<i>Bottom-up initiatives</i>			
Support community-led initiatives	✓	✓	✓
Promote grassroots funding opportunities and other resources		✓	
Provide dedicated support staff to the institutional publisher for the management of Diamond OA activities	✓		
Allocate dedicated time for researchers and academic staff to engage in Diamond OA editorial activities	✓		
Develop an inventory of Diamond OA activities in your institution	✓		
Co-develop a marketing strategy to improve the external visibility of institutional Diamond OA publishers	✓		
Explore inter-institutional collaborations on various aspects of Diamond OA publishing	✓		
Integrate Diamond OA publishing into institutional open science policies	✓		

1.0 Introduction

The recommendations and guidelines in [this report](#) have been developed to help institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers that support, or are willing to support, Diamond Open Access (OA) as a model for scholarly publishing. They were co-designed with institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers as part of the Horizon Europe project ‘Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication’ ([DIAMAS](#)).

The recommendations and guidelines are a comprehensive and flexible framework for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers to take action on Diamond OA. The framework is comprehensive, because it presents the full scope of actions that can be taken for a variety of different reasons, including supporting positive research cultures, taking economic and financial responsibilities, and acknowledging dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy.

The framework is also flexible, because organisations can prioritise the actions most important to them in the short and long term, depending on their goals and objectives. First, the recommendations presented in this document may have different implementation timelines. This is especially relevant for institutions, whose operations highly depend on national contexts, institutional readiness and specific organisational cultures. Second, the actionability of selected recommendations may differ depending on the type of institution, as funders, sponsors, and donors, universities, research performing organisations, and learned societies. Different governance structures, operational models or resources, including staff or social and technical infrastructures can significantly influence their ability to adopt these recommendations.

Supporting Diamond OA is a collective responsibility shared by institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers. While this report distinguishes between these groups, this approach was primarily intended to structure the co-design process, which aimed to understand the diverse needs, concerns, and opportunities identified by each stakeholder group. The analysis presented here highlights areas of priority that are common to many, emphasising that the recommendations and guidelines to support Diamond OA ultimately require collective action and collaboration across all these actors.

1.1 Background

The scholarly publishing landscape has become increasingly complex and diverse with the growth of open access. Shifting away from the traditional subscription-based publishing model, the research sector has had to navigate transformative agreements, article processing charges, and more.

The predominantly commercial approach to open access has raised urgent questions about its economic sustainability, while also introducing considerable inequities for

authors in terms of access to funds for publication, as well as problems of research integrity such as paper mills, research fraud, and retractions. The drawbacks of commercial approaches to open access suggest that scholarly publishing may increasingly require a firmer degree of control by both public authorities and the academic community.

Diamond publishing provides a promising alternative. While Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) follow a broad variety of practices, an important number of them focus on not-for-profit and community-owned publishing. Recently, Diamond OA has [captured the attention](#) of public sector organisations and policymakers as an institutional publishing model that explicitly rejects the extractive and inequitable nature of commercial models. Diamond OA is a [scholarly communication model](#) in which research outputs are openly available, without charging fees to either authors or readers. In this model, all content-related elements of publishing are directly controlled by the academic community and public institutions.

1.2 Co-designing the recommendations and guidelines

The recommendations and guidelines were developed together with and for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers through co-design processes led by the European University Association (EUA), Science Europe, and OPERAS respectively, which ran for one year between December 2023 and November 2024 (cf. table 1 infra). The two-fold objective of this process was to engage experts from institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers to co-design recommendations and guidelines, and engage their leadership in a strategic discussion on the future of Diamond OA.

Why were these recommendations and guidelines developed? Given the increasing momentum of Diamond OA, these recommendations and guidelines raise awareness among institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers and promote practical steps they can take to support this model for scholarly publishing. The DIAMAS project provided a framework to take this work forward. A key objective of this project is to support Diamond OA policies and strategies by engaging with institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers from across the research system. This ensures that the recommendations and guidelines are feasible and based on a good understanding of the stakeholders at hand.

Who are these recommendations and guidelines for? They have been developed together with and for European institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers that provide either financial, in-kind, or policy support to Diamond OA journals, publishing platforms, and repositories. Again, as indicated previously, supporting Diamond OA is a collective responsibility that is shared between these actors, with each of them playing an essential role in maintaining and developing this model.

- **Institutions** such as universities, other research performing organisations, and learned societies often act as a ‘parent organisation’ for institutional publishers and publishing services providers (IPSPs). They provide them with the staff on the one hand to provide a diverse set of services, including infrastructure, financial support, and the academic resources needed to maintain and operate Diamond OA outputs (journals, books and other publications), publishing platforms, and repositories on the other.
- **Funders, sponsors, and donors** are key actors in the fast-evolving scholarly publishing landscape, with their policies and investments ensuring that scholarly publishing is sustainable and provides societal value. This responsibility is especially important as studies ([here](#) and [here](#)) consistently highlight sustainable funding as one of the key challenges to support Diamond OA.
- **Policymakers** are key to facilitating Diamond OA, because they create regional, national, and EU-level policies that simultaneously support and incentivise funders, sponsors, and donors and institutional leaders in progressing the development of Diamond OA is crucial.

The co-design process initially aimed to develop recommendations and implementation guidelines, which is reflected in the title of this project deliverable. However, during this process, discussions with institutions, funders, sponsors, donors, and policymakers revealed that it was too early to create specific guidelines for implementing Diamond OA initiatives. The current ecosystem is experiencing a surge of new initiatives, many of which are exploring innovative approaches to support Diamond OA. It will take time for the insights gained from these innovations to mature and inform the development of implementation guidelines. As a result, the report focuses on providing general recommendations and guidelines, with implementation aspects included only where relevant. To address the absence of consistent implementation guidelines, the report highlights a collection of good practices that serve as inspiration.

Co-design with experts	
4 Dec 2023	Inception meeting with funders, sponsors, and donors (online)
13 Mar 2024	Focus group with institutional practitioners (online), further elaborated through two meetings of the EUA Expert Group on Open Science
16 Apr 2024	Co-design workshop with funders, sponsors, and donors (online), further discussed with funders, sponsors, and donor experts in the Science Europe Working Group on Open Science on 6 March, 27 June, 17 September, and 3 December 2024
30 Sep - 2 Nov 2024	Written Review Policy Suggestions for policymakers . Policy suggestions based on the input from the co-design sessions listed above were subject to a written review targeting policymakers, with this review serving as a co-design process itself

5 - 29 Nov 2024	Online consultation on the first draft of the set of actionable recommendations and guidelines for Diamond OA. The consultation targeted all stakeholders groups and feedback received were integrated into the text.
18 Nov 2024	Validation meeting "Creating actionable recommendations and guidelines for Diamond OA" with institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers (online)
Engage leadership	
12 Apr 2024	Workshop " The road towards Diamond OA " with institutional leaders (Swansea, United Kingdom)
28 Jun 2024	Consultation with national open science policymakers, discussion at Council for National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC) meeting
20 Nov 2024	High-level event with funders, sponsors, and donors during Science Europe General Assembly (Budapest, Hungary)

Table 1 - Co-designing recommendations and guidelines

2.0 Pathways to support diamond open access

What are the main pathways for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers to support Diamond OA? Before we turn to more detailed recommendations and guidelines, this part of the report outlines various pathways to provide broad support for the Diamond OA ecosystem. They focus on becoming involved in key initiatives that are shaping the landscape, and engaging with the communities that are forming at the local, national, and global level.

- Identify reasons and motivations to support Diamond OA and promote its benefits.** Research organisations and policymakers should explore and identify their main reasons and motivations to support Diamond OA, as well as the obstacles encountered in this pursuit. The three main reasons and motivations to support Diamond OA are explained in this report (cf. section 3 infra), and can serve as a starting point together with the [talking points](#) also developed as part of the DIAMAS project. Exploring ways to broaden and combine these reasons and motivations as part of an organisational strategy, will ensure more effective support (cf. ANR's model in table 2 infra). Institutional leaders, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers should also take the initiative to raise awareness among researchers and in researcher communities on the benefits offered by the Diamond OA publishing model, and the [sustainable](#) alternative it presents to traditional subscription-based and pay-to-publish OA models.

- **Enhance recognition and reward systems.** Research organisations and policymakers should establish and promote strategies to recognise and reward the contributions of editors, reviewers, and authors in Diamond OA publishing. These strategies should avoid perpetuating the current system's excessive emphasis on publication metrics (e.g. Journal Impact Factor, h-index), and instead align with the principles outlined in the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\) Commitments](#), and contribute to positive research cultures.
- **Invest in the development of monitoring systems and evidence-gathering initiatives.** Research organisations and policymakers should establish a strong evidence base through monitoring the landscape and evidence-gathering activities, which will be essential for advancing Diamond OA as the leading scholarly communication model for publicly funded research. Importantly, the gathered data should be openly accessible and internationally comparable, adhering to shared methodologies and principles.
- **Sign the Action Plan for Diamond OA.** Research organisations and policymakers should contribute to the growing Diamond OA community by endorsing the [Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#) (published in March 2022). Regular meetings are organised to keep this community informed of the latest initiatives and developments, give them a platform to engage in mutual learning and knowledge exchange, and discuss opportunities for collective action. These discussions emphasise the importance of strengthening the complementarity between the initiatives that are emerging in the Diamond OA landscape.
- **Support local, national, and community Diamond Capacity Centres.** Research organisations and policymakers should develop, implement, and expand support for local, national, and community Diamond Capacity Centres. A wide range of new and innovative practices and services are emerging in this regard, both those that serve specific national and disciplinary communities, and those that aim to cut across those boundaries to provide resources and services to a wider community that wishes to adopt and promote innovative publishing practices.
- **Engage in the European Diamond Capacity Hub.** Research organisations and policymakers should support Diamond OA communities at the national and European levels by engaging in the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) that was launched in January 2025. Alongside capacity hubs in other world regions, the EDCH federates and aligns national, disciplinary, and institutional capacity centres in Europe that deliver services and guarantee quality standards of Diamond OA journals in various languages and for a variety of disciplines.
- **Engage in the Global Diamond Open Access Framework.** Through the EDCH, research organisations and policymakers should also engage in the forthcoming Global Diamond OA Framework. This infrastructure will aim at providing resources and services to Diamond OA communities worldwide to strengthen their role in scholarly communication. It will be a global infrastructure serving

communities worldwide, operating as a distributed system that aligns diverse communities to achieve shared goals.

Integrating values and economics: ANR's model for supporting Diamond OA

The French National Research Agency (ANR) offers a compelling example of how research funding organisations can articulate and strengthen [their support for Diamond OA](#) by integrating diverse and complementary reasons. ANR's commitment, which is aligned with the [Second French Plan for Open Science](#) by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, highlights two key focuses. Firstly, ANR prioritises fostering positive research cultures. Their support for Diamond OA aims to promote bibliodiversity and a variety of scholarly publication pathways, and encourage multilingualism in research. This approach reflects their dedication to a more inclusive and pluralistic research ecosystem. Secondly, ANR underscores their economic and financial responsibility as a public research funding organisation. They emphasise the importance of sustainable funding models, cost transparency, and control, guided by their fiduciary duty to optimise public investment for societal benefit. This example demonstrates how combining diverse motivations, such as promoting research cultures and ensuring financial sustainability, can create a more robust case for supporting Diamond OA. By aligning economic considerations with the shared values and goals of the research community, ANR effectively reinforces the impact of its initiatives, illustrating a good practice approach for other organisations.

The role of capacity centres in the Diamond OA ecosystem

Capacity centres play an important role in the Diamond OA landscape, offering support to national and disciplinary communities. A variety of such centres have already been established or are under development. Examples include [HRČAK](#) in Croatia, [OpenEdition](#) in France, [openjournals.nl](#) in the Netherlands, and a new capacity centre in Germany supported by the [German Research Foundation](#) (DFG). Looking ahead, these centres have the potential to transcend national boundaries, providing resources and services to a wider community. This expansion could be facilitated by the [European Diamond Capacity Hub](#) (EDCH), launched in January 2025, which aims to coordinate and enhance collaboration across capacity centres.

Developing inter-institutional collaborations in Diamond OA publishing: Universities SHARE platform

A strong example of inter-institutional collaboration in Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing is [Universities SHARE \(Scholarly Heritage and Access to Research\)](#), an open platform coordinated by the University of Naples Federico II and involving 11 Italian universities. This initiative fosters cooperation among academic institutions in both scholarly communication and library services. Universities SHARE operates on two complementary levels. First, it integrates the library services of the participating institutions by providing a shared catalogue in linked open data and an information discovery system, enabling seamless access to analogue and digital collections across partner universities. Second, it supports Diamond OA digital publishing, allowing universities to pool their resources for journals, e-books, research data, and

historical records. A key feature of this model is the mutual recognition of institutional users, granting them access to consultation, lending, and other services across all member institutions. While the platform is sustained by the participating universities, which provide funding for its infrastructure, editorial independence is safeguarded through a dedicated scientific committee that retains full control over the quality and content of the publications. To ensure a consistent standard of quality and transparency, Universities SHARE requires adherence to a minimum set of formal requirements, which are publicly available [here](#).

National policies and funds supporting Diamond OA: The (Second) French Open Science Plan and National Fund for Open Science

Policies supporting Diamond OA on a national level significantly impact the adoption and advancement of Diamond OA practices. Through its [National Plan for Open Science](#) (2021-2024), France has prioritised the support of Diamond OA. Dedicated to supporting Open Science principles, measures such as supporting no-fee publishing models, encouraging multilingualism, and establishing a dedicated [French National Fund for Open Science](#), which allocates financial resources to establish and sustain OA infrastructure, have [proven to effectively support Diamond OA](#).

Research funders committing to Diamond OA: A DIAMAS case study report

More good practices have been collected by the DIAMAS project. Based on a series of dialogues with representatives from research funders, a [separate report](#) provides a set of insights into why and how funders are trying to support OA, specifically Diamond OA publishing.

Table 2 - Good practices by institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

3.0 Recommendations and guidelines

How can institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers support Diamond OA? To address this question, this report organises the recommendations and guidelines in separate, but related categories, which are explained in further detail in the [DIAMAS Synergy Report](#). These categories reflect the main reasons for research actors to support Diamond OA, including positive research cultures, economic and financial responsibilities, and dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy.

As mentioned previously, supporting Diamond OA is a collective responsibility shared by institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers. This report emphasises this by noting the complementary and essential roles of institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers for most, if not all, recommendations and guidelines. An overview of the recommendations and guidelines and the division of responsibilities is included in 'Recommendations and guidelines at a glance' (cf. supra).

3.1. Positive research cultures

Research organisations and policymakers share a responsibility to strengthen [positive research cultures](#) that reflect core values such as autonomy, freedom, care, collegiality, collaboration, equality, equity, diversity, inclusion, integrity, ethics, openness, and transparency. While these values are often implicit, supporting Diamond OA is a concrete way to affirm them. Journals, publishing platforms, and repositories within this model are led and owned by scholarly communities and serve a diverse range of typically multilingual and multicultural scholarly communities, reinforcing the principle of bibliodiversity. By its nature and design, Diamond OA promotes equity and inclusion in the creation and dissemination of scholarly knowledge.

- **Support multilingual and multicultural scholarly communities and their journals, repositories, and publishing platforms**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Establish grants and offer in-kind and other support specifically designed to support Diamond OA outputs, platforms, and repositories that publish in the local language or multiple languages, ensuring that non-English research is accessible and valued, as well as engaging multicultural scholarly communities. In addition, seek to encourage serving broad research communities, including and specifically addressing under-represented and marginalised groups and publishers that serve local or multiple languages. This approach can be implemented through policy and financial support, e.g. through structural funding and by starting up new efforts through grants. Valuing linguistic, societal and cultural diversity in scholarly publishing and thereby preserving epistemic cultures can help reduce bias in knowledge production and increase the impact of research.

- **Organise initiatives to promote the benefits of Diamond OA in your institution**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Organise initiatives that promote the benefits of Diamond OA in institutions, including targeted training sessions, workshops and information events for researchers based on the [DIAMAS Toolsuite](#), as well as reports on [contractual, in-kind, and voluntary work](#) in Diamond OA. Such activities should also improve the [researchers' understanding](#) of the different OA publication models (Gold, Green, Diamond, etc), including their costs, benefits and potential risks as outlined in [UNESCO's outlook report](#). In implementing this recommendation, institutional leaders should collaborate closely with their institutional publishers and relevant institutional departments. Resources such as the [EUA's new university Open Access checklist](#) can also be instrumental in offering a detailed overview of the current opportunities and challenges within the scholarly communication landscape.

- **Ensure that your institution's Diamond OA publisher adheres to rigorous quality standards**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Encourage institutional publishers to use the [DOAS self-assessment tool](#) developed by the DIAMAS project, which helps institutional publishers evaluate their alignment with high-quality Diamond OA standards.

- **Raise awareness about the importance of finding and choosing high-quality Diamond OA publication venues**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Inform researchers and academics about the opportunity to publish their research results in Diamond OA outlets. To facilitate this, institutional leaders should ensure that clear guidelines are available in the institution. Support and training should also be offered to find and publish in Diamond OA outlets. In particular, they should be instructed on how to select Diamond OA publishers that adhere to rigorous quality standards, helping them ensure the credibility and impact of their research publications.

- **Advocate for a more equitable scholarly publishing ecosystem, including Diamond OA through policy change and action**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for policymakers

Encourage the development of Open Access or publication policies to highlight the importance of a wide range of publishing venues, including Diamond OA, in publicly funded research. Collaborate with national policymakers (e.g. via CoNOSC) to build a consensus around the importance of Diamond OA and help develop policies that reflect this priority. Policies should be coupled with clear guidelines, incentives, and recognition to ensure their implementation. OA policies and advocacy for them should be based on a good understanding of the Diamond OA publishing sector and researcher's information practices.

3.2 Economic and financial responsibilities

Research organisations and policymakers must address economic and financial responsibilities to ensure that scholarly publishing is sustainable and provides societal value. For public organisations, this is a key part of their fiduciary duty to ensure that public funds are optimally invested and lead to societal benefits. Diamond OA offers a sustainable funding model, characterised by cost transparency and control. Unlike profit-driven, extractive practices in other models, Diamond OA is led and owned by scholarly communities. This approach ensures a better return in public investment, maximising the societal impact of research funding.

3.2.1 Sustainable funding

- **Make long-term funding commitments**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Provide multi-year funding mechanisms to ensure the long-term financial stability and sustainability of Diamond OA initiatives, reducing reliance on project-based funding that is limited in time. Whether it is structural funding from institutions to support institutional publishers within their organisations, or government investments in the broader ecosystem, the goal is to provide sufficient and predictable funding streams to support the development of institutional, national, and international initiatives and infrastructures. Conversely, research organisations and governments should also allow for short-term flexibility through innovation grants and pilot programmes to develop, test, and refine innovative approaches to Diamond OA publishing, with the potential for wider adoption.

- **Develop collaborative funding initiatives**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Encourage collaboration between institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and other actors to pool resources and support Diamond OA initiatives [sustainably](#). These collaborations can develop bilaterally or multilaterally, and can also benefit from the cooperation developing at European and global level through the EDCH and Global Diamond OA Framework (cf. section 2 supra).

- **Encourage institutions to repurpose savings from institutional, regional or national publishing deals**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for policymakers

Encourage institutions to repurpose savings from agreements such as institutional, regional or national publishing deals, read and publishing deals, and subscriptions, or from (temporarily) cancelling such deals, to strengthen the national and international Diamond publishing ecosystem and community-owned, shared infrastructure for equitable and trustworthy scholarly communication.

- **Consider exploring strategies for a more sustainable budget allocation for the institution's scholarly communication activities**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Reflect on the opportunity of redirecting institutional funding from for-profit publishing to Diamond OA activities, especially now that agreements with for-profit publishers are becoming increasingly unsustainable for institutions. Implementing a budget reallocation will be instrumental in supporting the long-term sustainability of

institutional publishers. However, such a shift should be implemented through a carefully evaluated step-by-step approach. In particular, fostering a cultural shift will be crucial to ensure the reallocation of the money effectively supports Diamond OA publishing. Institutional leaders should see the support of national funders and policymakers, especially in those countries where traditional publishing models continue to be prioritised in the assessment of research and academic careers.

- **Seek to innovate funding mechanisms to support improvements in digital transformation**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for policymakers

Advocate for change in funding regulations to allow for greater flexibility in supporting digital and open access initiatives. Review policies to ensure that funding mechanisms are aligned with the needs of the digital age, enabling support for innovative models like Diamond OA, funding international infrastructure not based in the research funder's country. Promote best (digital) practices for Diamond OA.

- **Support open, inclusive and community-owned databases**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions and policymakers

Policymakers should invest in the development and widespread adoption of open, inclusive, and community-owned research information systems that serve many, including for example the EDCH, [Public Knowledge Project](#) (PKP), and the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#) (DOAJ). Institutions also have a role to play in ensuring that academics and researchers are aware of such community-owned databases. These include institutional Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and repositories, as well as global publication and citation databases like [OpenAlex](#), [OpenCitations](#) and [OpenAIRE](#). Such databases ensure the visibility of globally and locally relevant research, regardless of language and adhere to the principles of the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) and the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure \(POSI\)](#).

3.2.2 Cost transparency and control

- **Require transparent financial reporting**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Require Diamond OA journals, publishing platforms, and repositories to provide detailed and transparent financial reports to ensure accountability and responsible use of funds, in alignment with relevant procedures at different levels.

- **Invest in cost-effective publishing solutions**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Invest in the development and implementation of cost-effective publishing technologies and practices that reduce operational costs while maintaining quality.

3.3 Dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy

When supporting Diamond OA, research organisations and policymakers must take into account the dynamics of authority, patronage, and legitimacy. This includes both top-down support, such as political, financial, and logistical backing from national authorities and funding bodies, and bottom-up initiatives driven by universities, research institutions, and scholarly communities, including learned societies. In recent years, political support for Diamond OA has grown, particularly from [European governments](#) and [UNESCO](#). At the same time, research communities have called for collective action, as seen in their endorsement of the [Action Plan for Diamond OA](#).

3.3.1 Top-down support

- **Advocate for public policies**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Advocate for regional, national, and international policies that encourage the adoption of Diamond OA as the leading scholarly communication model for publicly funded research. Institutions and organisations should be encouraged – e.g. through national publishing strategies – to strengthen a more equitable publishing system, including Diamond OA or the establishment of a national organisation aimed at coordinating Diamond OA efforts, to collaborate on various aspects of Diamond OA publishing. These collaborations could include developing and utilising shared resources, making joint funding applications, carrying out coordinated efforts to develop and maintain OA infrastructure through in-kind contributions or direct funding, and joint implementation.

- **Engage in international collaboration**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Participate in and support international initiatives, consortia, and projects that promote Diamond OA on a European and global scale and establish a shared monitoring and evidence-base for its further development. Examples include: first, at European level, the EDCH (cf. section 2 supra), which aims to strengthen the Diamond OA community in Europe by supporting European institutional, national, and disciplinary capacity centres and Diamond publishers and service providers in their mission of

Diamond OA scholarly publishing; and second, at global level, the Global Diamond OA Framework (cf. section 2 supra) being developed by UNESCO. To enhance understanding the landscape of Diamond OA, it is highly advised to facilitate and collaborate in international, national, and regional projects that work on joint advocacy, explore the scope of the Diamond OA publishing landscape, and collaborate on joint services.

- **Create opportunities for knowledge exchange and networking**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Organise, support, and attend conferences, workshops, and networking events focused on Diamond OA to facilitate the exchange of good practices and innovative ideas, and build networks between actors at regional, national, and international level. Examples include: first, the community webinars organised to foster information exchange between the endorsers of the [Action Plan for Diamond OA](#); and second, the Global Summits on Diamond OA that so far took place in [Toluca, Mexico in October 2023](#) and [Cape Town, South Africa in December 2024](#), and have been instrumental in bringing together global partners and align their positions on key elements of Diamond OA.

- **Strengthen Diamond OA through strategic funding and funding strategies**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Build capacities for Diamond OA through strategic funding focused on enhancing shared services and open research infrastructure while leveraging economies of scale. Collaborative funding strategies on the international, national and regional level are needed to reduce fragmentation and enhance the capacities of the Diamond OA community. This can be achieved by many actors (e.g., charities, national research funders or agencies, information research providers and institutions) collaborating for bigger causes that aim to support international services and infrastructures that serve many. Funding is necessary to develop and support regional capacity hubs such as the EDCH as well as local and national capacity centres or cross-country regions (e.g., the Nordic countries), to help scale up Diamond OA. Enable the EDCH to collaborate with other regional hubs via the Global Diamond OA Framework. Support national capacity centres in their efforts to innovate and implement new practices that serve local and national communities and foster diversity through community-led initiatives. Recognise scholarly communication platforms and services as research infrastructures and include them in national and international research infrastructure roadmaps.

3.3.2 Bottom-up initiatives

- **Support community-led initiatives**

This is a shared recommendation for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers

Support community-led initiatives and networks that promote Diamond OA, fostering a sense of ownership and engagement among researchers across all disciplines and communities, with a view to collectively solve common challenges, i.e. develop Diamond OA capacity, drive change in the research community, and more.

- **Promote grassroots funding opportunities and other resources**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for funders, sponsors, and donors

Create funding opportunities and other resources specifically for grassroots Diamond OA initiatives proposed by researchers and scholarly communities, encouraging innovation and responsiveness to the specific needs of local communities. Diamond Capacity Centres (cf. section 2 supra) can play an important role in this regard, also providing technical assistance to help new and existing Diamond OA outlets to improve their operations and sustainability.

- **Provide dedicated support staff to the institutional publisher for the management of Diamond OA activities**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Provide institutional publishers with professional staff needed to ensure the smooth operation of institutional publishing activities, while safeguarding their editorial and scientific independence. Providing such support is not only crucial to curate Diamond OA outputs, but also to improve their recognition across the scientific community and, therefore, their value for the institution itself. While support should come from the institutional level, leaders can also encourage institutional publishers to engage with national-level infrastructures and services for Diamond OA publishing, which can provide additional support and resources to perform publishing activities.

- **Allocate dedicated time for researchers and academic staff to engage in Diamond OA editorial activities**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Explore alternative ways to recognise and reward the editorial and peer-review work of researchers for Diamond OA outputs, including those published by other institutions such as learned societies, while also integrating contributions to Diamond OA into academic and research evaluation processes at institutional, and national level. Non-monetary compensations, such as allocating dedicated time for Diamond OA activities, can play an important role in supporting and acknowledging the voluntary editorial work put into institutional publishing. Providing researchers and academics

with the time needed to curate their Diamond OA activities will also be important to ensure that their publications are in line with high-quality standards and practices.

- **Develop an inventory of Diamond OA activities in your institution**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Develop an inventory that includes information such as a list of Diamond OA outputs published by the institutional publishers, details on the number of issues or articles published annually and Information about editorial boards and peer review practices. The aim of the inventory is to provide institutional leaders with a clearer understanding of the needs, challenges and opportunities associated with the institutional publishers operating within their organisation. Building this awareness will allow institutional leaders and institutional publishers to collaborate more effectively. This will also create pathways to maximise the impact and reach of the institution's Diamond OA activities, promoting them both within and outside the institution. Institutional leaders can refer to the Diamond OA publisher typologies compiled in the [DIAMAS Synergy Report](#).

- **Co-develop a marketing strategy to improve the external visibility of institutional Diamond OA publishers**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Collaborate with institutional publishers and editors to develop a clear strategy on how to ensure the visibility and findability of the Diamond OA outputs published by the institution. This will be instrumental in attracting contributions from different institutional, disciplinary and national contexts. Institutional leaders should also ensure that their institutional publishers are part of the [EDCH Registry and Forum](#), which will provide opportunities for the exchange of experiences, good practices and resources on several Diamond OA publishing-related topics.

- **Explore inter-institutional collaborations on various aspects of Diamond OA publishing**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Support institutional publishers in looking for opportunities to collaborate with other institutions and their publishers to pool resources, share costs and exchange good practices. Promoting the creation of inter-institutional collaboration can help different institutional publishers address common challenges, such as limited funding and resources, while also complementing the support provided by individual institutions. However, such an approach should also be supported by the creation of targeted measures at national level, which can include the development of a national strategy to strengthen Diamond OA or the establishment of a national organisation aimed at coordinating Diamond OA efforts.

- **Integrate Diamond OA publishing into institutional open science policies**

This recommendation is primarily relevant for institutions

Ensure that Diamond OA publishing is regulated by institutional policies that address open science practice. Such policies should include provisions related to publishing practices, financial support, quality assurance and peer review, legal and copyright issues, and training and awareness. This will be instrumental in supporting a more strategic approach to strengthening the institutional publisher operating within the institution, as well as promoting Diamond OA initiatives among researchers and academics working in the institution.

4.0 Concluding remarks

The recommendations and guidelines presented in this report are both a call to action and a roadmap for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers to collectively support Diamond OA as a sustainable, equitable, and community-driven model for scholarly communication. The comprehensive and flexible framework outlined here enables these actors to prioritise actions aligned with their specific goals, operational contexts, and resources, while contributing to the broader development of a thriving Diamond OA ecosystem.

Diamond OA offers a diverse, inclusive, and equitable alternative to commercial approaches to open access, addressing critical challenges such as economic inequities, sustainability concerns, and issues of research integrity. By placing the academic community and public institutions at the heart of scholarly publishing, Diamond OA fosters transparency, trust, and a commitment to advancing knowledge for the benefit of all.

As highlighted throughout this report, supporting Diamond OA is a collective responsibility. While distinct roles and approaches exist for institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers, their success in advancing Diamond OA ultimately depends on collaboration and shared accountability. The co-design process that informed these recommendations has already demonstrated the value of unified efforts, serving as a foundation for continued dialogue and collective action.

Looking ahead, it is essential for stakeholders to engage proactively in implementing these recommendations, aligning them with local, national, and international policies and initiatives. By doing so, they can help build an open, sustainable, and equitable future for scholarly publishing, ensuring that research outputs remain a shared public good.

This report marks the beginning of a journey – a step toward real change in scholarly communication. The DIAMAS project and the contributions of its diverse stakeholders underscore the momentum and potential of Diamond OA. With continued commitment and collaboration, institutions, funders, sponsors, and donors, and policymakers can

play a pivotal role in shaping a publishing landscape that upholds the principles of accessibility, equity, and integrity.

